

Proving the Sum of Alternative Harmonic Series

Chinnaraji Annamalai
School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

The harmonic series is given below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots$$

The alternative harmonic series is shown below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots - \frac{(-1)^{k+1}}{k} + \dots$$

The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$i.e. \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Let us prove the sum of alternative harmonic series as follows:

$$\text{Let } S = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

$$\Rightarrow xS = x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots$$

$$\text{Then, } (S - xS) = 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S.$$

$$i.e. \frac{1}{1 - x} = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

First, let us find the solution of $\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx$.

$$\text{Let } u = 1 - x; du = -dx; dx = -du.$$

$$\text{Then, } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\text{Now, } \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = -\ln(1-x) \Rightarrow -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1-x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)).$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Hence, proved.